

Perceived Influence of Information and Communication Technology Facilities on Business Education Students Entrepreneurial Intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the perceived influence of ICT facilities on business education students' entrepreneurial intention in polytechnics in North-East Nigeria. Business education prepares students for paid jobs and for self-employments through equipping them with knowledge of ICT facilities to enable them have entrepreneurial intention to reduce unemployment. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study was anchored on the theory of planned behaviour. The study adopted explanatory mixed method research design. The population was 1003 respondents, comprising 103 lecturers, 874 students and 26 class representatives in polytechnics in North-East Nigeria. The random sampling techniques was used to select 37 lecturers, 207 students and 9 class representatives, the sample of the study was therefore, 253. A 54-item questionnaire with 4-point rating scale was the instrument used for quantitative data collection. A structured interview was used to collect qualitative data. The instruments were face and content validated by three experts. Cronbach Alpha procedure was used to test the reliability of the instrument and the result yielded a reliability coefficient index of 0.88. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed among others that access to ICT facilities influenced business education students entrepreneurial intention with weighted average mean and standard deviation scores of 3.22 and 0.60; Microsoft Word skills influenced business education students entrepreneurial intention to a high extent with a grand calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation scores of 3.37 and 0.56. The findings on all the two hypotheses tested revealed that there were significant differences in the mean ratings of federal and state institutions regarding access to ICT facilities and Microsoft Word skills on business education students entrepreneurial intention ($t_{238} = 10.812, P < 0.05, 8.75$). Based on the findings of the study it was recommended among others that TETFUND and managements of polytechnics should ensure that ICT facilities are always available for effective and efficient teaching of business education students so that they will be motivated to have entrepreneurial intention.

Keywords: ICT, Facilities, Business Education, Entrepreneurial intention.

Introduction

Education holds the key to human progress. It plays an important role in bringing change. Education is one and only instrument that can be used to bring about change towards the social and economic betterment of a nation. Technology has changed the way and manner in which everything is done both in business, offices and education. ICT facilities have become the main tools and have a revolutionary impact on how the world is conceived and how people live in the world. Currently, the place of ICTs in the contemporary education and the world in general cannot be overemphasised. Modern businesses are conducted and facilitated through the use of ICT facilities such as telephones like handsets, land lines, fax machines, computer, computer networks like the internet, Google Scholar, email and so on (Oyewole, Afolabi and Olaniyi, 2021). The authors maintained that the phenomenon has evolved into e-commerce, e-banking, e-office, e-government, e-machine and e-education among others. ICT refers to diverse set of technological tools and resources used to communicate, and to create, disseminate, store and manage information. Chidiobi (2015) averred that communication technologies are equipment such as computers, audio-visuals, internet facilities, multimedia computers, e-mail, electronic bulletin board that enables information to be transferred from the source to the users which tried to overcome natural barriers to transferable information like speed and distance. In most cases, these ICTs are available but not used by students due to lack of adequate ICT knowledge on the parts of educators who are required to transfer the knowledge to the recipients and sometimes they are not available and underutilized by learners.

Business Education provides the skills, knowledge, aptitude, attitudes and competencies necessary for effective employment in specific occupation as self-employers. Business Education is an aspect of vocational and technical education that is designed to prepare students for the world of work and for self-reliance. It is a programme of study that equips the students with relevant skills for self and societal development. Simply put together business education is the type of education that prepares the youths for occupational positions in various offices, be it government or private. It is education that prepares students for the world of work and the world of business. Ayelotan and Sholagbade (2014) described business education as a programme of instruction which consists of two parts: the Office Education (presently known as Office Technology and Management) for effective careers and the general business education program that provides students with information and competencies. It is a type of education which provides skills, knowledge and attitude necessary for effective employment in specific occupation. Shaibu, Oshioyegwe and Mbaegbu (2014) state that business education is the deliberate intent of teachers to inform students about economics and business concepts and skills that might be useful in later life. It is meant to equip the youths with certain economic and business concepts as a vehicle for better understanding and analysis of the dynamic business work. Etoneyeaku (2013) views business education as a formidable force that will equip individuals with appropriate skills, knowledge, abilities and competencies that will enable them to be self-employed and self-reliant which will lead to sustainable economic development. The bottom line is that business education is a special education which focuses on training the recipient to be relevant in the world of work either by being an entrepreneur or by working for another.

Entrepreneurial intention is a state of mind that directs and guides an individual towards the conception, development and implementation of new business enterprise (Katz, 2014). Entrepreneurial intention is the willingness of an individual to show entrepreneurial behaviour and engage in entrepreneurial activities related with self-employment initiative and new business start-ups. Individuals would select professions in entrepreneurship depending on their

judgments of its fit and desirability (Dohse, Walter and Asuamah, 2013). Some students may have entrepreneurial intention and the question is who is an entrepreneur? Entrepreneur is the coordinator of all other factors of production. He is the owner of a business who controls all aspects of his business.

Statement of the Problem

Nigerian government made some efforts to reduce unemployment rate through the introduction of information and communication technology and entrepreneurship as courses into the Business Education and other programmes of study in Nigerian tertiary education. The purpose of introducing these courses is that students can be equipped with ICT facilities skills for self-employment after graduation. Yet, the rate of unemployment keeps increasing at alarming rate on a daily basis. These graduates are seeing ideal without corresponding career possibilities and without recourse to use the knowledge of ICT facilities for entrepreneurial intention. It is important to note that the graduates of business education are expected to develop different entrepreneurial skills and abilities that will enable them start up small scale businesses if they are unable to find white collar jobs. It has not been so and their jobless condition has been linked to several forms of criminality. Business Education graduates who have gone through the undergraduates programme in higher institutions are expected to have acquired ICT facilities skills such as keyboarding skill, word processing skill, database management system skill, webpage design skill, desktop publishing skill and competencies that will enable them to own businesses and become employers of labour but this has not been so. The absence of these makes graduates to roam about the streets looking for white-collar jobs that are rarely available. It is against this situation that it becomes necessary for the researchers to conduct this study in order to determine the Perceived Influence of ICT facilities on Business Education students Entrepreneurial Intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the Perceived Influence of Information and Communication Technology Facilities on Business Education Students Entrepreneurial Intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine the extent to which:

1. access to ICT facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.
2. Microsoft Word skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study.

1. To what extent does access to ICT facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria?
2. To what extent does Microsoft Word skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses formulated, were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers and students in Federal and State polytechnics on the extent to which access to ICT facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers and students on the extent to which Microsoft Word skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) by Ajzen (1991)

This study is anchored on the theory of planned behaviour which was propounded by Ajzen in 1991. Intentions, according to the notion, provide insight into how new initiatives emerge. Individual's intention to establish a business are based on their personal appeal to beginning a business, the personal capability to start a business and the personal proclivity to act on his/her own decisions (Kruger, 2000). According to this theory an individual's intention is the most crucial immediate indicator of whether or not a person will undertake a given action, and the stronger the intention to engage in a behaviour, the more likely should be its performance. The theory postulated that an individual's ambition to execute entrepreneurial abilities and their capacity to make thoughtful choices among alternatives and make effective selections lead to necessary behaviour. The theory states that planned conduct is an addition to the theory of reasoned action on beliefs, attitudes and intentions as drivers of human behaviour (Ajzen, 2011). Intention is the best predictor of human behaviour since it shows how willing and ready a person is to try their hand at entrepreneurship. Therefore, an individual's intention to engage in entrepreneurial behaviour is created based on his or her positive or negative judgement of the behaviour.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

Information and communication technologies (ICT) is defined as a diverse set of technological tools and resources used to transmit, store, create, share or exchange information. Information and Communications Technology (ICT) is an extensional term for information technology (IT) that stresses the role of unified communications and the integration of telecommunications (telephone lines and wireless signals) and computers, as well as necessary enterprise software, middleware, storage and audiovisual, that enable users to access, store, transmit, understand and manipulate information. According to Rouse (2023), ICT is also used to refer to the convergence of audiovisuals and telephone networks with computer networks through a single cabling or link system. Rouse maintained that there are large economic incentives to merge the telephone networks with the computer network system using a single unified system of cabling, signal distribution, and management. ICT is an umbrella term that includes any communication device, encompassing radio, television, cell phones, computer and network hardware, satellite systems and so on, as well as the various services and appliances with them such as video conferencing and distance learning. ICT also includes analog technology, such as paper communication, and any mode that transmits communication.

Rouse (2023) upheld that ICT is a broad subject and the concepts are evolving. It covers any product that will store, retrieve, manipulate, transmit, or receive information electronically in a digital form (e.g., personal computers including smartphones, digital television, email, or robots). Information and Communications Technology (ICT) is the use of computing and telecommunication technologies, systems and tools to facilitate the way information is created, collected, processed, transmitted and stored. It includes computing technologies like servers, laptop computers and software applications, as well as the wired and wireless communication technologies that support telephones, the Internet, the Internet of Things (IoT) and the metaverse.

Information and Communication Technology Facilities

Education is a systematic process of impacting knowledge through the improvement of knowledge and expertise in a particular area (Oyewole, Afolabi & Olaniyi, 2021). ICT facilities are very imperative in education because it is used in equipping students with skills for self-reliance. The knowledge and competencies obtained in the use of ICT facilities in the

training of business education students enable students to have various entrepreneurial skills that prepares them for self-reliance. When students are properly trained with ICT facilities, skills and competences will be the result and these will encourage the students to have entrepreneurial intention. The intention to work in public offices after graduation in this 21st century learning should be discarded by students. Business educators should endeavour to encourage entrepreneurial intention in students by equipping them with various skills that will induce them to set up businesses. Among the different forms of education business education which is an aspect of vocational and technical education is of unique nature because it deals with acquisition of skills that prepares individuals for practical and applied skills in different occupations.

Business Education

According to Okeke (2023), Business education is a branch of education that involves teaching the skills and operations of the business industry. This field of education occurs at multiple levels, including secondary and higher education. Consequently, the mission of business education at the college and the university level is to train the necessary manpower for industry, business, public and private business establishments, including manpower for teaching. Thus, business education opens various career opportunities to its graduates namely, teaching in schools at various levels depending on the level of degree obtained, working in commerce and the public sector of the economy, undergoing advanced studies in business, taking up management positions in various organizations and developing training programmes for industries and businesses. Business education is a major component of vocational education. Business education is also design field of study for the development of skills, attitudes, appreciation, creativity as well as creation of awareness and competencies in the office work and business world. It is a programme of study that equips students with relevant skills for self and societal development. Simply put together business education is the type of education that prepares the youth for occupational positions in various offices, be it government or private. It is education that prepares students for the world of work and the world of business (Ekpenyong, 2011).

Nnaji (2014) concurred that business education is education for and about training in business skills, competencies required for use in business offices, clerical occupations and that which gives occupational identity. The author maintained that business education is an academic programme offered at the tertiary level of education in Nigeria that is directed towards empowering learners with business skills. Njoku (2015) explained that business education is a programme of instruction, which consists of office education, which is a vocational education programme for office career workers through initial refresher and upgrading education. He further explained that general business education is a programme that provides learners with information and competencies which are needed by all in managing personal business affairs and in using the services of business.

Entrepreneurial Intention

The willingness of an individual to show entrepreneurial behavior and engage in entrepreneurial activities related with self-employment initiative and new business start-ups is characterized as entrepreneurial intention. Individuals would select professions in entrepreneurship depending on their judgments of its fit and desirability (Dohse, Walter and Asuamah, 2013). In a similar vein, Barringer and Ireland (2010) claimed that people will choose a career in entrepreneurship if they believe it will help them fulfil their personal goals, pursue their ideas, and make financial benefits. Entrepreneurial intention reflects an individual's state of mind targeted at new venture creation, development of new business

models, and value addition within existing business models. It is a reflection of inner courage, ambition, and a sense of independence, that an individual's potential to become an entrepreneur may not find expression unless they have intentions (Zain, Abubakar and Salwa, 2014). It is assumed that the choice to start a new business has been planned for some time and is thus preceded by the intention to do so. However, in the opinions of Ajzen (2015) in some circumstances, this intention is created only moments before a decision is made, while in others the intention never leads to real behavior. As a result, entrepreneurial intent is thought to predict individual decisions to start their own businesses.

Methods

The mixed method research design was adopted for the study. The Explanatory Confirmation design was employed for the study. The descriptive research design was employed for the quantitative aspect of the study since it sought to document and describe what exists or the present status of existence or absence of what was investigated (Nworgu, 2015). The population of the study for the quantitative data comprises 103 OTM lecturers and 874 students in Polytechnics in the North-East. For the qualitative data, OTM class representatives in these polytechnics were used and they are 26 in number making the total population of the study 1,003 OTM lecturers and students respectively. The simple random sampling technique was used to select 37 lecturers out of the 103 population of lecturers and 207 students out of 874 population of students for the quantitative study while 9 class representative out of 26 population of class representatives were selected for the qualitative study. The total sample of the study was therefore, 253. The research instruments was structured questionnaire and semi-structured interview which was developed by the researchers after proper review of literature. The 54-item questionnaire was titled "Perceived Influence of ICT Facilities on Students Entrepreneurial Intention Questionnaire (PICTFSEIQ)." The Questionnaire was structured on a 4-point rating scale of Very High Extent, High Extent, Moderate Extent and Low Extent with corresponding values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The second instrument was the interview schedule which was used to collect the qualitative data. Interviews goes a long way in helping research subjects to open up and air their views in a very magnificent way based on their experiences on what is being investigated (Egbri, 2015).

The instruments were face and content validated by three experts. Two from the Department of Office Technology and Management the Polytechnic, Bali, one from Department of Measurement and Evaluation Taraba State University. The researchers conducted a pilot study at Kaduna Polytechnic. Twenty (20) Copies of the questionnaire were administered to lecturers and students in the department of Office Technology and Management. The data generated from the pilot study was analysed using Cronbach Alpha reliability method to determine the internal consistency of the instrument and it yielded a reliability co-efficient index of 0.88. The quantitative data was collected by the researchers with the help of one research assistant from each of the polytechnics under study. The researchers briefly explained to the research assistants how to administer and retrieve the questionnaires. The questionnaire and the interview schedule were administered simultaneously. The 37 copies of the questionnaire for lecturers were all collected and properly filled and used for the study. While out of the 207 copies of questionnaire administered to students 203 were returned and properly filled and used for the study which represents (98.06%) return rate.

Mean and Standard Deviation were employed to analyse the data which were collected to answer the research questions. The null hypotheses was tested using t-test at 0.05 level of

significance at the relevant degree of freedom. Decision rule with respect to research questions was based on the principle of upper and lower limits of the mean. Thus:

SECTIONS B1-B4:

Very High Extent	4	3.50 – 4.00
High Extent	3	2.50 – 3.49
Low Extent	2	1.50 – 2.49
Very Low Extent	1	1.00 – 1.49

Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the degree of responses; any item with standard deviation of less than 1.96 indicated that there was not much variability from the mean or from the responses of the respondents. On the other hand, any standard deviation above 1.96 indicated that there are wide variations in the responses of the respondents. The data collected from the interview was analysed using content analysis. Any null hypothesis whose p-value is equal or greater than the Alpha value ($0.05 \geq$) and at the derived degree of freedom was retained and concluded that there was no significant difference between the respondents otherwise it was rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: To what extent does access to ICT facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria?

Table 1: Summary of the mean ratings of respondents on the extent to which ICT facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

S/N	Item Statements	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	Access to World Wide Web (www) encourages students entrepreneurial intention	3.48	0.58	High Extent
2.	Access to electronic mail supports students entrepreneurial intention	3.55	0.50	Very High Extent
3.	Access to Internet aids students entrepreneurial intention	3.20	0.65	High Extent
4.	Access to computer facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.53	0.50	Very High Extent
5.	Access to printer facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.41	0.49	High Extent
6.	Access to flash drives, CD-Roms and DVD-Roms facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.43	0.54	High Extent
7.	Access to Excel Software facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.38	0.65	High Extent
8.	Access to Electronic Fund Transfer (ETF) facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.10	0.67	High Extent
9.	Access to Mobile phone facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.30	0.60	High Extent
10.	Access to Word Processing Software facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	2.83	0.91	High Extent
11.	Access to Data Base facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.42	0.63	High Extent
12.	Access to voice message system, audio and video	3.30	0.54	High Extent

recorder facilitates students entrepreneurial intention			
13. Access to facilities that help create and manage websites encourages students entrepreneurial intention	3.44	0.51	High Extent
14. Access to photocopier facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.24	0.60	High Extent
15. Access to desktop publishing facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	2.00	1.16	Low Extent
16. Access to Adding Machine facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	2.73	0.94	High Extent
17. Access to franking machine facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.52	0.62	Very High Extent
18. Access to multimedia projector facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.29	0.57	High Extent
19. Access to facsimile facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.32	0.47	High Extent
20. Access to teleconferencing facilitates students entrepreneurial intention	3.36	0.48	High Extent
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation	3.22	0.60	High Extent

Source: Field survey, 2023

Analysis of data in Table 1 shows mean and standard deviation of respondents responses on the extent to which access to ICT facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in polytechnics in North-east, Nigeria. The table reveals that respondents indicate that all the items except for item 15 are access to ICT facilities which influence business education students entrepreneurial intention in polytechnics in North-east to a high extent with mean scores of (3.48, 3.55, 3.20, 3.53, 3.41, 3.43, 3.38, 3.10, 3.30, 2.83, 3.42, 3.30, 3.44, 3.24, 2.73, 3.52, 3.29, 3.32 and 3.36 respectively). Respondents responses indicate low extent on access to desktop publishing facilitates students entrepreneurial intention with a mean score (2.00). The Table shows a grand calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation scores of 3.22 and 0.60 respectively. This implies that access to ICT facilities influence business education students entrepreneurial intention to a high extent (mean = 3.22, SD = 0.60).

Research Question 2. To what extent does Microsoft Word skills acquisition influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria?

Table 4: Summary of the mean ratings of respondents on the extent to which Microsoft Word skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

S/N	Item Statements	Mean	SD	Remark
1.	Create new documents using Microsoft Word	3.48	0.50	High Extent
2.	Copy, cut, edit and paste documents using Microsoft Word	3.39	0.54	High Extent
3.	Using a password to protect document	3.36	0.42	High Extent
4.	Backup documents and publications on CDs, DVDs in Microsoft Word	3.53	0.50	Very High Extent
5.	Save and open documents in Microsoft Word	3.39	0.64	High Extent
6.	Delete and retrieve a saved document in Microsoft Word	3.44	0.54	High Extent

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7. Print documents using Microsoft Word	3.32	0.47	High Extent
8. Use spell check to make corrections in Microsoft Word	3.50	0.50	Very High Extent
9. Upload information in Microsoft Word	3.58	0.50	Very High Extent
10. Ability to use Microsoft Word for word processing	3.18	0.67	High Extent
11. Ability to highlight a document or part of a document	2.73	0.94	High Extent
12. Ability to operate the keyboard	3.54	0.50	Very High Extent
Grand Mean/Standard Deviation	3.37	0.56	High Extent

Source: *Field Survey, 2023.*

Analysis of data in Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of responses on the extent to which Microsoft Word skills acquisition influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. The Table reveals that respondents agreed to all the constructs that Microsoft word skills acquisition influence business education students entrepreneurial intention to a high extent with mean scores of (3.48, 3.39, 3.36, 3.53, 3.39, 3.44, 3.32, 3.50, 3.58, 3.18, 2.73 and 3.54 respectively). The table shows a grand calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation scores of 3.37 and 0.56 respectively. This implies that Microsoft Word skills influences business education students entrepreneurial intention (mean = 3.37, SD = 0.56).

Hypotheses Testing

HO1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers and students in Federal and State polytechnics on the extent to which access to ICT facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of t-test of the difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students in Federal and State polytechnics on the extent to which access to ICT facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	Df	p-value	Decision
Lecturers	37	4.00	0.00	10.812	238	0.000	Ho1 Rejected
Students	203	3.07	0.52				

Source: *Field survey, 2023*

P < 0.05

The data in Table 3 reveals that 37 respondents are lecturers while, 203 respondents are students. The respondents that are lecturers have higher mean score but lower standard deviations ($\bar{x} = 4.00$; SD = 0.00) than students who have ($\bar{x} = 3.07$; SD = 0.52). The responses of the respondents are close to the mean as the standard deviations are very low. The table revealed that there was significant difference between the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent to which access to ICT facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East ($t_{238} = 10.812$, $P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students in federal and state polytechnics on the extent to which access to ICT

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facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East was rejected. This implies that lecturers and students of business education differ in their responses regarding the extent to which access to ICT facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in the North-East, Nigeria.

HO2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers and students on the extent to which Microsoft Word skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria.

Table 4: Summary of t-test of the difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent to which Microsoft Word skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	Df	p-value	Decision
Lecturers	37	4.00	0.00	8.75	238	0.000	Ho2 Rejected
Students	203	3.27	0.50				

Source: Field survey, 2023

$P < 0.05$

The data in Table 4 reveals that 37 respondents are lectures while, 203 respondents are students. The respondents that are lecturers have higher mean score but lower standard deviations ($\bar{x} = 4.00$; $SD = 0.00$) than the students respondents ($\bar{x} = 3.27$; $SD = 0.50$). The table reveals that there was significant difference between the mean responses of lectures and students on the extent to which Microsoft Word skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria ($t_{238} = 8.75$, $P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent to which Microsoft Word skills influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria was rejected. This implies that lecturers and students of business education differ in their responses regarding the extent to which Microsoft Word skills influence business education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in the North-East, Nigeria.

Analysis of the Qualitative Data

The qualitative data are analysed using content analysis and the identified themes are related to the purpose of the study since the interview was semi-structured. The themes are access to ICT facilities and Microsoft Word skills influence business education students entrepreneurial intentions in polytechnics in North-east.

Access to ICT

The qualitative data collected on how access to ICT facilities influence Business Education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria reveals that all the nine participants representing 100% said that access to ICT facilities greatly influence business education students entrepreneurial intention. The class representatives said access to ICT facilities will induce entrepreneurial intention in students because access to ICT facilities is very important if one wants to be an entrepreneur in this contemporary world. One out of the nine participants said that once students are equipped with ICT facilities and the skills to operate these facilities, students will be quick to conceive intention for self-reliance since there

is no paid jobs available for the graduates. This is in line with respondents responses in the quantitative analysis of the study.

All the nine respondents expressed interest in entrepreneurship if access to ICT facilities are given to them. They also said it is through business education that students can be prepared for entrepreneurship especially in this 21st century where ICT and ICT facilities are the order in the society.

Microsoft Word Skills

All the class representatives representing 100% of the participants revealed that Microsoft word skill is the enabling skill for entrepreneurial intention especially to Office Technology and Management business education student. The class representatives explained that Microsoft Word skills is very important to OTM students who are expected to have entrepreneurial intention in business centres where documents can be typed in Microsoft Word. Knowledge and skills in this package is very essential because it will assist the students who have entrepreneurial intention to navigate through the package and produce documents easily. One of the class representatives said that Microsoft word is essentially made for office managers who are expected to use it effective in the office for paid job or for self-employment.

Discussion of Findings

The study was on the perceived influence of information and communication technology facilities and skills on business education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. This discussion is based on the two research questions and two hypotheses presented and statistically analyzed in the study. The findings concerning research question and hypothesis one revealed that lecturers and students of business education in the departments of OTM in North-east Nigeria, agreed that access to ICT facilities and skills influence business education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. The findings also, revealed that there was substantial difference between the mean ratings of lecturers and students in federal and state polytechnics regarding influence of ICT facilities and skills in business education students entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students in the federal and state polytechnics on the extent to which access to ICT facilities and skills influence business education students entrepreneurial intention was rejected.

This corroborates with the study of Pratt (2023) who stated that ICT's influence on business and management has been profound. From streamlining operations and enhancing decision-making to enabling new business models and fostering global collaboration, technology has become an integral part of both modern enterprises and small businesses. This is also confirmed by the study of Oyewole, Afolabi and Olaniyi (2021) who affirmed that ICT facilities are very imperative in education because it is used in equipping students with skills for self-reliance.

The findings concerning research question and hypothesis two revealed that lecturers and students of business education in the departments of OTM in North-east Nigeria, agreed that Microsoft Word skills influence business education students entrepreneurial intention in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. The findings also, revealed that there was substantial difference between the mean ratings of lecturers and students in federal and state polytechnics regarding influence of Microsoft Word skills in business education students entrepreneurial intention. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and students on the extent to which Microsoft Word skills influence business education students entrepreneurial intention was rejected. This is in line with the findings of Ekpenyong (2011) who said that among the different forms of education

business education which is an aspect of vocational and technical education is of unique nature because it deals with acquisition of skills that prepares individuals for practical and applied skills in different occupation.

Conclusion

Conclusions in this study are made based on the findings from the analysis which revealed the influence of ICT facilities on business education students entrepreneurial intention, which are important to lecturers and students especially in this period of high rate of unemployment. ICT facilities and Microsoft word skills are very important assets to business education students because they greatly influence their entrepreneurial intention. Business education lecturers must make use of ICT facilities in teaching so that business education students will be equipped with ICT skills. Microsoft word skill is very essential to OTM student therefore, lecturers should ensure that the students are equipped with this skill, whilst this is done business education students will have the interest to be entrepreneurs after graduation since the required skills have been acquired. This is necessary because contemporary education requires learners to be skilled, to enable graduates to be self-employed in order to curb the dearth of unemployment.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are advanced to channel the way forward:

1. TETFUND and managements of polytechnics should ensure that ICT facilities are always available for effective and efficient teaching of business education students so that they will be motivated to have entrepreneurial intention.
2. Lecturers should ensure that Microsoft Word package is effectively and robustly taught to business education students in order to prepare and induce entrepreneurial intention in them.

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